

Zigzag Text Alignment

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Among the four basic typographic alignments—flush left (ragged right), flush right (ragged left), justified, and centered[1]—the justified alignment delivers the highest reading comprehension. Justified alignment, however, has a shortcoming. Most of us have experienced reading a justified paragraph with many lines, and at some point, we unintentionally skip the next line and either read the same line again or skip the subsequent line. To address this shortcoming of justified alignment, this work introduces a new zigzag-style typographic alignment. In this zigzag alignment style we propose to maintain the justification but arrange the lines in a zigzag style (as shown in this paragraph). We observed that our zigzag text alignment addresses the issue of locating the next line by subconsciously training a reader to look for a protruding line on the left when returning the gaze from a protruding end of the previous line on the right. Similarly, the reader is also automatically trained to look for an indented line when returning the gaze from an indented end of the previous line on the right. As such, the zigzag alignment style alleviates the issue of unintentionally skipping the next line. Also, it is a common practice to separate paragraphs by indenting the first sentence in paragraphs. With the zigzag alignment, however, such an indentation can no longer be used to separate paragraphs. Instead, an extra blank line is needed to separate paragraphs. The zigzag style could be immediately helpful to those who read longer journal articles and to the proposal writers who submit many pages of plain text content to funding agencies such as the US National Institutes of Health (NIH) and the US National Science Foundation (NSF). We surveyed a group of 10 students and faculty members at the University of Missouri-St. Louis to determine if this style reduces the issue of unintentionally skipping lines. Since everyone who was surveyed independently asserted that this was indeed the case, we did not consider performing a rigorous survey experiment. We propose that this alignment style be offered in word processing software such as Microsoft Word and Open Office Writer.

Availability

An open-source and free version of a L^AT_EX script for zigzag alignment, which allows changing the depth of the zigzag style, is available at <https://github.com/ba-lab/zigzag-justify>. An example Overleaf template (<http://overleaf.com>) ready to write a report is also publicly available at the same link.

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Reference

- [1] Robert Bringhurst and Richard Eckersley. The elements of typographic style. *Journal of Scholarly Publishing*, 31(3):149, 2000.